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Analysis of Aerofoil profile for Optimal Wind Turbine Design to Harness Wind energy

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ABSTRACT

Amidst growing global demands for sustainable energy sources, wind energy is being constantly harnessed through wind turbines as a cleaner source of energy. The blade design of these turbines provide a myriad of scope to be modified and optimized for increased efficiency, enhanced power capture, sustainability and cost effectiveness. Parameters like aerodynamic profile, pitch, blade material etc. of a wind turbine plays a vital role in improving blade design for further optimization. Among these variables, aerofoil profile of the blade possesses significant potential to introduce and integrate optimal changes to the constantly changing wind turbine designs, thus, paving the path for further research to achieve more efficient wind turbine models. This paper aims to discover and enlighten the possibilities of improving the blade design of a wind turbine through accurate choice of blade profile, that can open the door to further experiments of harnessing wind energy efficiently through utilizing the aerodynamic effects on these blade profiles. Throughout this investigation, feasibility of various aerofoil profiles, such as-NACA, FX etc. and hybrid profiles (combination of various profiles) for blade design will be analyzed by simulating the aerofoil cross-section in CFD for calculating the resultant aerodynamic variables, such as-lift, drag and torque generated through the turbine, which are crucial for determining the efficiency of a wind turbine. The wind velocity can affect the data generated in ambient conditions, which will also be taken into account in this investigation to demonstrate the potential of these wind turbine designs to harness wind energy amidst mild to severe weather conditions. The comparison of the blade profiles will be conducted through the generated data, which will facilitate the outcome of this paper of illustrating the pros and cons of each blade profiles amongst the few choices considered for wind turbine optimization, thus, facilitating the choice of more efficient and stable blade profile for integration into the existing wind turbine models and enable these to harness enhanced wind energy.

KEYWORDS: Blade, Optimization, Aerofoil, CFD, Simulation

NOMENCLATURE

P	Power	[W]	ω	Angular Velocity	[rad/s]
T	Torque	[N-m]	v	Wind Velocity	[m/s]
r	Turbine Radius	[m]			

1. INTRODUCTION

Wind turbine is a rotary mechanical device, in which torque, i.e. rotary motion or power is harnessed through the use of wind flowing over it, which is then transferred to a generator to produce electricity, thus leading to a successful utilization of the renewable energy source.

Depending on the wind velocity, the degree of energy harnessed through wind turbines can vary, along with other parameters affecting this process, such as-turbine blade material, blade profile, turbine structure etc. Blade profile refers to the cross-section of the blade, which is a parameter with myriad of choices but can significantly influence the degree of lift and drag force acting on the wind turbine and the torque generated by it based on that choice. Wind turbine can be classified into horizontal and vertical axis turbines, of which

horizontal models are widely investigated for further optimization through varying a crucial parameter, i.e, the aerofoil profile of the blades. Most widely uses blade profiles are-NACA, SG, FX, BW, RAF etc., each with their individual pros and cons. This paper aims to delve deeper into the feasibility and pros and cons of various blade profiles through simulating the 3D blade models in CFD using SOLIDWORKS flow simulation and compare the lift, drag and torque data generated through the simulations. At a first glance, more torque generation may conceptualize more efficiency, however, parameters like lift and drag force can also contribute to the optimization factors, as higher lift forces in wind turbine blades may cause instability within the structures, thus, exposing it to failure during harsh weather conditions. Comparison of the simulated data will facilitate the investigation of these factors and enable the outcome of this analysis, which will be vital in reaching a logical and concrete verdict on the appropriate choice of blade profile for wind turbine optimization.

Due to the scarcity of non-renewable energy in the modern energy craving civilization, renewable energy has become a necessity rather than a surplus reserve considering the future energy crisis. As such, research and investigations are continuously being conducted on increasing the production and efficiency of this new energy sector. The study of aerofoil profiles in this analysis will contribute to that goal and might even provide further and newer loopholes and parameters to be studied on, which can pave the way to more and better designs regarding wind turbine optimization, that has the potential to increase the efficiency and degree of harnessing wind energy in the renewable energy field for higher amount of electricity generation in a cleaner way to avert the scarcity of energy in the near future.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous studies on the optimization of horizontal axis wind turbines have been conducted through the analysis of various aerofoil profiles, such as-DU93-W-210,FFA-W3-301 and S(NREL)-series(S809,S821,S835 etc.) for incorporation into wind turbine blades in an attempt to realize a more efficient model[1-2].In addition, NACA aerofoil profile has been a prime choice in past investigations for integration in wind turbine models, illustrating their pros and cons in the process[3,4].However, considering the numerous aerofoil profiles available in modern aerodynamics database, these studies leave a room for further optimization of the blades depicted and introduction of novel design models through incorporation of newer aerofoil profiles that possess potential for harnessing higher degree of wind power but still remain uninvestigated due to lack of broader approach. Despite of ANSYS fluent being the primary choice for CFD analysis and investigation of aerofoil profiles in studying their wind energy harnessing capabilities in past investigations[5],relevant softwares, such as-SOLIDWORKS flow simulation interface can serve as a noteworthy substitute for conducting simulation of the designed wind turbine models due to its simplicity and accuracy, leading to generation of required data within a short time while avoiding the difficulties of mesh limitations and complexities involved in ANSYS interface, which is worth investigating. Concept of blade outer periphery modification was introduced in a study for multi-objective optimization of the wind turbine by the integration of various aerofoil profiles within a single blade [6], that facilitated the scope of designing blades with unique peripheries by varying the aerofoil profile and their segment ratios, which is attempted in this study for realizing an optimized model. Curved blades has proved to be the most optimal choice for 3-blade wind turbine designs over the years compared to rounded ones due to their ability to rotate at high speeds swiftly owing to the rapid flow of air over the curved peripheries[7],that will play a key role in facilitating the choice of aerofoil profiles utilized in this paper.

Analyzing the limitations and scope for wind turbine modification evident from the previous studies,this paper aims to illustrate more optimal choices of aerofoil profile suitable for integration in wind turbine blade designs through introduction of newer, previously unexplored profiles, such as- RAF 89,B29 root, FX 77 series etc. In addition, our analysis is attempted at studying and testing the characteristics of a novel wind turbine blade model, designed by utilizing the outer periphery modification concept mentioned in previous studies and introduce a far efficient and stable model compared to the conventional wind turbines that permit incorporation of a few frequently used aerofoil profiles only, prioritizing curvier aerofoil profiles in the process due to their higher torque generation capabilities. The study of aerodynamic effects on these blade models and their torque generation potential will be investigated using SOLIDWORKS flow simulation, which will motivate the future CFD researchers to shift towards simplicity for their simulation-based analysis, accelerating their activities through lowering the time consumption and nullifying complications.

3. METHODOLOGY

The entire analysis of this paper can be summed up as the combination of the following logical and systematic segments illustrated in figure-1, which is provided to enable the readers get a general overview of the whole process:

Figure 1: Flowchart of the adapted tasks to complete the proposed analysis

3.1 Design and rendering of the model

The 3D model of the turbine blades proposed were designed and assembled in a 3-blade orientation using SOLIDWORKS and rendered in Keyshot to enhance the view. The blades are 5.5 m long, with aerofoil profile ratios varying with each dimensional gaps to realize a modified blade design. Including the central circular dome of 1.5 m diameter to support the blades, the fully assembled wind turbine covers a diameter of 13.8 m. The outer periphery of the blade consists of curves adapted to blend with the varying aerofoil profile ratios, giving the blades modified and unique overall designs. For the hybrid blade design, FX 77 W343, RAF 89, B29 and NACA 4424 aerofoil profiles were integrated into a single blade, arranging them from root to tip in a descending order of their degree of curved surfaces, with more segments of FX 77 W343 incorporated than other profiles to realize higher degree of drag on the proposed model and generate more torque. The blade profile and rendered models are provided in figure-2 to give a better understanding of the design approach.

Figure 2: (a) Blade profile, (b) Hybrid blade profile, (c) Rendered 3D blade model and (d) 3D wind turbine model proposed for the analysis

All the blade models including our proposed hybrid one has the same profile segment ratios and distances, with an exception in the hybrid model incorporating multiple profiles in a single blade.

3.2 Running Simulation on the Blades and Turbine models

Utilizing the flow simulation interface in SOLIDWORKS, the blades were placed under a wind velocity attack of 5 m/s in the positive x-axis, which created pressure distributions on the blade surfaces to generate lift and drag forces on them. The efficiency of a wind turbine lies in its ability to generate enough torque, i.e. power utilizing the incoming air flow for transmitting to energy conversion devices, such as generators and as a result, facilitating the exploitation of power from a cleaner source of renewable energy. Thus, to investigate the torque producing capability of each of the proposed blade models, they were subjected to air flow comprising of varying wind velocities depending on the surrounding weather conditions ranging from light to strong breeze. The CFD analysis was done by allowing the air to flow in the direction of positive x-axis, which causes the turbines to rotate and generate the data of torque produced as a result, that can be used to calculate the harnessed power according to the following equation :

$$P = T\omega \tag{1}$$

The magnitude of angular velocity generated can be determined using the following formula :

$$\omega = \frac{v}{r} \tag{2}$$

The resultant CFD interfaces illustrated below provides a visualization of the analysis performed in calculating the lift and drag forces acting on each blade models and the torque generated by each of the turbine models.

Figure 3 : (a)Lift and Drag Analysis on blade profiles and (b)Torque calculation of the turbine models using SOLIDWORKS flow simulation

3.3 Recording and Analysis of resultant data

The CFD analysis conducted as mentioned will develop data on the lift and drag forces acting on the blade profiles and also the torque generated by each of the blades when they are incorporated into wind turbine structures, which will be crucial in understanding the pros and cons of each model. The analysis and comparison of the tabular data will provide a better picture to the readers about the potential of the proposed models to be implemented in practical scenarios and will support this study's verdict on the most efficient turbine model that is worth utilizing in renewable energy sectors for harnessing more wind energy through the introduction of more optimal models

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Through the simulation of the proposed blade and wind turbine models in CFD interface using SOLIDWORKS flow simulation, the data depicted in tables-1 and 2 were generated, which were analyzed for realizing a verdict of our study on wind turbine optimization.

Table 1. Lift and Drag force acting on each designed blade profiles in Newtons being subjected to wind velocities under varying weather conditions

Wind Velocity	2 m/s (Light Breeze)		4.5 m/s (Gentle Breeze)		6 m/s (Moderate Breeze)		9 m/s (Fresh Breeze)		12 m/s (Strong Breeze)	
Blade Profile	Lift	Drag	Lift	Drag	Lift	Drag	Lift	Drag	Lift	Drag
RAF 89	-0.095	0.959	-0.882	4.751	-1.474	8.358	-3.415	18.65	-6.83	32.825
B29 Root	-0.283	0.767	-1.352	3.738	-2.173	6.594	-5.777	14.43	-11.0	25.507
FX 77 W343	0.825	1.552	4.556	7.632	8.492	13.58	19.26	30.49	30.54	53.695
NACA 4424	-0.183	1.048	-1.129	5.206	-2.465	9.182	-5.981	20.53	-12.0	36.267
Hybrid Blade	-0.050	1.315	0.611	6.512	2.510	11.35	-0.183	25.81	-0.63	45.848
NACA 0012	-0.046	0.433	-0.249	2.107	-0.804	3.679	-2.174	8.182	-8.77	14.329

Table 2. Torque generated by the designed turbine blades in N-m under varying weather conditions

Wind Velocity	RAF 89	B29 Root	FX 77 W343	NACA 4424	Hybrid Blade	NACA 0012
2 m/s (Light Breeze)	4.528	4.061	5.472	3.649	4.648	0.929
4.5 m/s (Gentle Breeze)	22.441	22.23	27.559	17.381	24.603	3.609
6 m/s (Moderate Breeze)	40.332	37.704	51.97	28.151	43.937	7.754
9 m/s (Fresh Breeze)	86.794	72.331	114.15	54.599	96.815	18.447
12 m/s (Strong Breeze)	154.488	118.834	186.049	103.472	170.079	33.081

The study and analysis of any wind turbine model for optimization is aimed at increasing the drag force acting on it to enable the generation of higher torque while reducing the resultant lift force to minimize the instability, thus, lowering the risk of failure in the process of harnessing more wind energy. The resultant data of the CFD analysis conducted in this study highlights NACA 0012 as the least capable of fulfilling both criteria simultaneously, whereas, RAF 89 blade provides an acceptable balance between the two, making it worth implementation in wind turbine models instead of the traditional NACA blades for more frequent practical applications. To increase the power generation, NACA 4424 and FX 77 W343 are excellent models, with FX 77 W343 far surpassing the NACA model in terms of power output from mild to extreme weather conditions. However, both the models possess a large affinity for lift forces, with FX 77 W343 being particularly susceptible to failure due to vibration and instability even in mild weathers due to very high lifts, while the NACA 4424 blade can be considered reasonably stable at mild conditions. As such, to broaden the extent of our analytical study in investigating newer aerofoil models for incorporation in wind turbines to realize optimization, we proposed a hybrid model integrated with multiple aerofoil profiles for combining each of their individual pros and cons in an attempt to reach an optimal solution. According to the simulation data illustrated in tables-1 and 2, our hybrid model generates the least amount of lift at varying weather conditions compared to other conventional models, while at the same time, its torque generation capability is in between the NACA 4424 and FX 77 W343 blades, resulting in an excellent substitute of the investigated models, that fulfils both criteria of an optimal and efficient wind turbine. Thus, thorough analysis of the study conducted in this paper concludes that, the hybrid model proposed in this study is an upgrade of the traditional wind turbine models capable of harnessing considerably higher amount of energy for power generation while nullifying the risk of failure in harsh weather conditions. These characteristics make this model to be considered for implementation in practical wind mills at regions where rough weather persists for a larger period of the year, thus, utilizing the high amount of wind energy available without any further costs and time consumption incurred in

repairing the failed wind turbines due to instability, thus, increasing the region's power generation capacity by manifold through appropriate utilization of valuable wind energy available in severe weathers that are lost due to inability of the existing wind turbine models to sustain their structural integrity as a result of higher lift forces acting on them and resulting in vibration and failure.

5. CONCLUSION

To counter the ongoing energy crisis in the 21st century and beyond, renewable energy has been a hot topic for further investigations, research and studies for achieving more modified, efficient and eco-friendly models of the existing wind turbines as it is considered the cleanest and most cost-efficient source of energy to harness and utilize in energy sectors. The investigation conducted in this paper is aimed towards that goal, in an attempt to introduce and realize a more efficient horizontal axis wind turbine model through the incorporation of frequently overlooked aerofoil profiles, even though having significant potential to exploit more wind energy than the conventional ones. As expected, some of the profiles indicated more torque generation capacity than the typical NACA profile and in the process, a unique, newer and more efficient blade model was realized through the integration of various aerofoil profiles into a single blade, paving the path for further investigation and research into the potential of this model. The hybrid model introduced in this paper incorporated more curved profiles close to the blade root and less curved ones towards the blade tip, to generate more drag, resulting in higher torque, however, the vice versa requires comprehensive investigation to compare the efficiency with our proposed model. Incorporation of more curved profiles midway between blade tip and root is another concept worth analyzing for turbine blade optimization. Our study involved a few of numerous available aerofoil profiles, which leaves a broader opportunity for incorporating other curved models, such as FX series, Joukowski0021-JF etc. into our depicted hybrid model to study their wind energy harnessing capabilities in an attempt to realize more efficient models. Lastly, feasibility of our introduced models including the hybrid blade for implementations in practical scenarios is worth a thorough analysis for achieving the desired outcome of this study, which is the realization of larger energy generation through harnessing wind power more efficiently. To conclude, it is expected that the findings of this study can contribute to the field of wind turbine model optimization through addressing the limitations and shortcomings introduced in our paper, which will prove to be vital in implementing optimal and modified models in various regions with abundance of wind energy to harness wind energy more efficiently.

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